

Dysphagia-optimised intensity-modulated radiotherapy versus standard intensity-modulated radiotherapy in patients with head and neck cancer (DARS): a phase 3, multicentre, randomised, controlled trial

Journal

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Impact factor =41.6

Authors

Christopher Nutting is a British Professor of Clinical Oncology and medical consultant, specializing in head and neck cancers, who has helped develop Intensity-Modulated Radiotherapy (IMRT), an advanced form of Radiation therapy. **H-index- 61**

Keith Rooney is a researcher and scientist who is notably involved in the field of medical research, particularly focusing on oncology and related clinical studies. **H-index-7**

Tom Roques is a researcher and scientist, but as of my knowledge cutoff in 2023, there isn't a widely recognized profile of him in mainstream scientific databases. **H-index- 36**

Devraj Srinivasan is a researcher and scientist who is typically associated with the field of medical research, particularly in oncology and cancer treatment. His work may involve clinical studies, innovative therapies. **H-index- 3**

Justine Tyler is a researcher and scientist whose work is primarily focused on areas related to cancer research, particularly in the context of improving patient outcomes through clinical trials, cancer treatment strategies, and possibly molecular biology. **H-index-5**

Emma Hall is a researcher who has been involved in medical and clinical research, particularly in the area of oncology. **H-index- 59**

Imran Petkar is a researcher who has worked in the fields of oncology and clinical research, with a focus on cancer treatment and improving patient outcomes. **H-index-8**

Robert Frogley is a researcher involved in medical research, particularly in the fields of oncology and clinical trials. **H-index-21**

Bernadette Foran is a researcher who appears to be involved in medical research, particularly in areas related to oncology and clinical trials. **H-index-11**

Emma De Winton in the context of scientific or academic contributions. It's possible that she is involved in specialized or emerging areas of research, possibly in the fields of oncology, clinical research, or other areas of medicine, given the context of many other names you've asked about. [H-index-14](#)

Audrey Cook is a researcher involved in more specialized fields or emerging areas of science, possibly in oncology, clinical trials, or other aspects of medical research. [H-index-7](#)

Cheng Boon is not a widely recognized name in major scientific databases or publications. It is possible that he is an emerging researcher or involved in specialized or niche areas of scientific study, such as oncology. [H-index-14](#)

Article summary

Objective:

- The primary goal of this study was to assess the efficacy of dysphagia-optimised intensity-modulated radiotherapy (DO-IMRT) in improving swallowing function in patients diagnosed with oropharyngeal and hypopharyngeal cancers.
- The aim was to see whether DO-IMRT could reduce the radiation dose to areas critical for swallowing and aspiration, while still being as effective as standard IMRT in treating cancer.

Study Design:

- The research was a phase 3, multicenter, randomized, controlled trial, conducted across 22 radiotherapy centers in the UK and Ireland.
- A total of 118 participants, aged 18 years and older, with T1-4, N0-3, M0 oropharyngeal or hypopharyngeal cancer were enrolled in the study.
- Participants were randomly assigned to receive either DO-IMRT or the standard IMRT, with the allocation being masked to both patients and speech language therapists involved in the treatment.

Radiotherapy Protocols:

- For standard IMRT, radiation was delivered to the tumor and surrounding areas as per typical protocols.
- In the case of DO-IMRT, special attention was paid to minimize radiation exposure to the pharyngeal muscles involved in swallowing, like the superior and inferior pharyngeal constrictor muscles.
- DO-IMRT aimed to maintain a radiation dose of no more than 50 Gy to critical swallowing-related structures, thus reducing the risk of long-term swallowing dysfunction.

Primary Outcome:

- The primary endpoint of the study was the MD Anderson Dysphagia Inventory (MDADI) composite score, which was measured at 12 months after completing radiotherapy.
- The MDADI score is a widely used tool for evaluating the severity of dysphagia (swallowing difficulty) and its impact on quality of life. Higher scores indicate better swallowing function.
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Results:

- The study showed that patients in the DO-IMRT group reported significantly better swallowing function than those in the standard IMRT group. Specifically, the mean MDADI composite score was higher for the DO-IMRT group (77.7) compared to the standard IMRT group (70.6), with a statistically significant difference ($p=0.037$).
- This result demonstrates that DO-IMRT not only reduces radiation exposure to critical swallowing structures but also significantly improves swallowing function as reported by patients.

Adverse Events:

- Both treatment groups reported serious adverse events, but these were similar between groups and did not result in any treatment-related deaths.
- The most common side effects included hearing impairment, dry mouth, and dysphagia. However, the incidence of these side effects did not differ significantly between the two groups, with slightly fewer severe adverse events observed in the DO-IMRT group.

Conclusion:

- The findings of this study suggest that DO-IMRT is an effective treatment approach for patients with pharyngeal cancers, as it improves swallowing function while delivering effective cancer treatment.
- DO-IMRT should now be considered as the new standard of care for these patients undergoing radiotherapy for pharyngeal cancers, as it offers significant improvements in quality of life by reducing swallowing difficulties and preserving swallowing function post-treatment.